

ISCT

View Abstract

CONTROL ID: 3893773**TITLE:** DEVELOPMENT OF REPROGRAMMING PROTOCOLS FOR EQUINE INDUCED PLURIPOTENT STEM CELLS (IPSCS): FIRST STEPS TOWARDS A ONE MEDICINE STRATEGY FOR OSTEOARTHRITIS**AUTHORS (FIRST NAME, LAST NAME):** [Laura Barrachina](#)¹, Aisling O'Brien¹, Tarlan Eslami Arshaghi¹, Ana Ivanovska¹, Mary Murphy¹, Frank Barry¹**INSTITUTIONS (ALL):** 1. Regenerative Medicine Institute (REMED), University of Galway, Galway, Galway, Ireland.**ABSTRACT BODY:**

Background & Aim: Osteoarthritis is a major contributor to disability in humans and to chronic lameness in horses. Induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) can be used for therapy but pre-clinical knowledge is limited to small animals. Equine joints better resemble human features and horses can benefit from cell therapy as patients. To develop a One Medicine approach, the first goal is to establish eqiPSCs from new sources with potential chondrogenic commitment, such as articular chondrocytes, umbilical cord blood MSCs and foetal MSCs. The varying requirements in different species make it necessary to develop reprogramming protocols for equine cells, which ideally would be serum-free and feeder-free to facilitate clinical application.

Methods, Results & Conclusion: Equine cells were retrovirally transduced with OSKM factors and plated onto a feeder-free layer (Geltrex) or feeder cells (inactivated mouse embryonic fibroblasts, iMEF) with serum-free media (knock out [KO] or E8 StemFlex), or medium containing FBS. KO and FBS media were supplemented with bFGF and LIF.

Cells cultured in FBS showed morphological changes and areas of positive alkaline phosphatase (AP) staining, but did not form colonies. Cells in E8+Geltrex formed granulated colonies but after 2-3 passages produced embryoid body-like structures with differentiated borders and partial AP staining. Cells cultured with KO and Geltrex or iMEF formed AP+ iPSC-like colonies but the lines were not stable. KO+iMEF promoted better morphology but after a few passages initiated differentiating with decreased AP staining. Transduced cells showed transgene expression, which was maintained after plating in serum-free conditions but not after picking colonies. However, cells cultured in KO+iMEF expressed endogenous Oct4 up to passage 2.

In summary, OSKM transduction of equine cells led to morphological and gene expression changes suggestive of iPSC reprogramming, but fully reprogrammed eqiPSC lines could not be established. Nevertheless, KO+iMEF supported more consistent iPSC-like morphology while E8+Geltrex, which are widely used in human iPSCs, did not work in the equine species. Understanding pluripotency networks in animals is key to provide appropriate conditions for reprogramming. Our ongoing work is using a lentiviral OSKM cassette to improve the delivery of reprogramming factors, along with specific inhibitors to facilitate pluripotency induction. This work illustrates the significant challenges associated with generation of iPSCs in veterinary species.

PRESENTATION TYPE: Oral or Poster**CURRENT CATEGORY:** iPSC**CURRENT SUB-CATEGORY:** Basic science and preclinical studies**KEYWORDS:** Horse, Cartilage, iPSC.

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Medical Tourism Disclosure: Confirmation Accordance with ISCT's Position**Medical Tourism Disclosure:** Confirmation of All Author's Approval**AWARDS:**

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INTRODUCTION & OBJECTIVES

- Osteoarthritis is a major contributor to disability in humans and to chronic lameness in horses → iPSCs can be used for therapy but pre-clinical knowledge is limited to small animals.
- Equine joints better resemble human features (models) + horses can benefit from cell therapy (patients) = **One Medicine**
- In order to develop a One Medicine approach for osteoarthritis, our first goal is to establish equine iPSCs from new sources with potential chondrogenic commitment:

- Umbilical cord blood MSCs
- Articular chondrocytes
- Embryo-derived MSCs

The varying requirements in different species make it necessary to develop iPSC reprogramming protocols for equine cells, ideally serum-free and feeder-free to facilitate clinical application

METHODS & RESULTS

Retroviral reprogramming

INCOMPLETE REPROGRAMMING → STRATEGIES TO IMPROVE GENERATION EQUINE iPSCs

Lentiviral reprogramming

Abbreviations: iPSC: induced pluripotent stem cell; MSC: mesenchymal stromal cell; CB: umbilical cord blood; FBS: foetal bovine serum; AP: alkaline phosphatase; Tg: transgene; Endog: endogenous; iMEF: inactivated mouse Embryonic fibroblasts; KORS: knock-out replacement serum; LIF: leukaemia inhibitory factor; bFGF: basic fibroblast growth factor; MOI: multiplicity of infection; GFP: green fluorescent protein; EB: embryo-derived; AC: articular chondrocytes

CONCLUSIONS

Reprogramming system

- Retroviral reprogramming (single factors) → lower transduction, less control
- Lentiviral reprogramming (cassette) → higher transduction, more control

Culture conditions

- Knock-out media (LIF + bFGF) + feeder cells → works better for equine iPSCs
- Inhibitor cocktail did not enhance reprogramming and decreased proliferation

However, neither the reprogramming system nor the culture conditions seemed to be the most important → **Origin of cells**

- Clear superiority of **embryo-derived cells** over perinatal and adult cells → Endogenous expression of pluripotent factors can enhance reprogramming → In spite of presenting the lowest transduction efficiency (*intrinsic resistance to virus infection?*)

This work illustrates the significant challenges associated with the generation of iPSCs in veterinary species
Understanding pluripotency networks in animals is key to provide appropriate conditions for reprogramming